

COMPARISON OF INTER-APPOINTMENT PAIN REDUCTION DURING ROOT CANAL TREATMENT IN SYMPTOMATIC APICAL PERIODONTITIS BY USING CONVENTIONAL IRRIGATION AND ENDOACTIVATOR IRRIGATION SYSTEM: A RANDOMIZED CONTROLLED TRIAL

Dr. Noorullah Soomro¹, Prof. Dr. Zahid Iqbal², Dr. Aosaf Anwar³, Prof. Dr. Salman Shafique⁴

¹BDS, FCPS Part-II resident, Operative Dentistry & Endodontics, Isra University Hospital, Hyderabad, Sindh, Pakistan

²BDS, FCPS, Professor & Head of Department, Operative Dentistry & Endodontics, Altamash Institute of Dental Medicine, Karachi, Pakistan

³BDS, FCPS, Assistant Professor, Operative Dentistry & Endodontics, Isra University, Hyderabad, Sindh, Pakistan

⁴BDS, FCPS, Professor & Head of Department, Oral & Maxillofacial Surgery, Isra University, Hyderabad, Sindh

¹nsoomro@hotmail.co.uk, ²zahidig@hotmail.com, ³aosafanwar88@hotmail.com,
⁴salman.shafique@israuniversity.edu.pk

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Corresponding Author: *

Dr. Noorullah Soomro

Abstract

Objective: To compare inter-appointment pain reduction during root canal treatment in symptomatic apical periodontitis by using conventional irrigation and EndoActivator irrigation system.

Methodology: This randomized controlled trial enrolled 156 patients diagnosed with symptomatic apical periodontitis involving permanent mature single-rooted teeth that were randomly allocated into two equal groups at Department of Operative Dentistry and Endodontics, Isra University Hospital, Hyderabad, over one year following synopsis approval. Group A underwent conventional syringe irrigation, while Group B received EndoActivator irrigation. Pain intensity was recorded using the Visual Analog Scale preoperatively and postoperatively at 24 and 48 hours. Percentage inter-appointment pain reduction was calculated and compared between groups using independent samples t-test. Stratification by age, gender, and tooth type was performed, followed by post-stratification analysis. SPSS version 22 was used to analyse the data. A p-value of ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results: A total of 156 patients were included, with 78 participants in each group. The EndoActivator irrigation group demonstrated significantly greater percentage pain reduction than the conventional irrigation group at both 24 hours (82.01 ± 14.91 vs. 49.49 ± 12.22 ; $p < 0.001$) and 48 hours (99.17 ± 4.22 vs. 82.64 ± 13.37 ; $p < 0.001$). Statistically significant differences remained after stratification for age, gender, and most tooth types. In canine teeth, the difference remained statistically significant at 24 hours but not at 48 hours.

Conclusion: EndoActivator irrigation was associated with significantly greater inter-appointment pain reduction compared with conventional syringe irrigation during root canal treatment.

INTRODUCTION

The primary objective of endodontic treatment is the thorough disinfection of the root canal system (RCS) to eliminate infection and promote healing. This is achieved through biomechanical preparation (BP), irrigation with antimicrobial solutions, and intracanal medication. However, due to the complex anatomy of the RCS, mechanical instrumentation alone cannot adequately debride all canal irregularities, necessitating the use of chemical irrigation to dissolve necrotic debris and smear layers effectively. [1,2]

Pain management during root canal treatment remains a critical concern for clinicians. Inter-appointment pain, particularly in cases of symptomatic apical periodontitis, is influenced by mechanical and chemical factors, including the choice of irrigation technique and solution. [3,4] Studies indicate that conventional needle irrigation, though widely used, has limitations in effectively delivering irrigants beyond the needle tip, leaving residual bacteria in anatomical complexities such as fins, isthmuses, and lateral canals. [5] In response, advanced irrigation devices have been developed to enhance disinfection and improve patient outcomes.

The EndoActivator system (Dentsply, USA) is a sonically driven irrigation device designed to enhance irrigant penetration and agitation. By generating acoustic streaming and cavitation effects, it improves smear layer and biofilm removal within complex root canal anatomy. [6] Recent studies suggest that EndoActivator irrigation may contribute to significant inter-appointment pain reduction due to its superior ability to disrupt microbial biofilms and enhance debridement. [7,8]

Given the limited data comparing inter-appointment pain reduction between conventional irrigation and EndoActivator irrigation in cases of symptomatic apical periodontitis, this study aims to provide evidence on the efficacy of these two techniques. The

objective of this randomized controlled trial is to compare the impact of conventional irrigation and EndoActivator irrigation on inter-appointment pain reduction in patients with symptomatic apical periodontitis.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was conducted as a randomized controlled trial (experimental study). The research was carried out in the Department of Operative Dentistry & Endodontics, Isra University Hospital, Hyderabad. The study was completed within one year following the approval of the synopsis. The sample size was determined using WHO software. A previous international study [9] reported a 52.3% reduction in preoperative pain at 24 hours in the conventional irrigation group compared to a 79.4% reduction in the EndoActivator irrigation group. At 48 hours, pain reduction was 87.6% in the conventional irrigation group and 95.5% in the EndoActivator group. Based on these statistics, with a 95% confidence interval, power of 80%, and a significance level of $P < 0.05$, the total sample size was calculated to be 306 patients, with 153 patients for each group. A non-probability consecutive sampling method was used for patient selection. The inclusion criteria were healthy individuals of all genders between the ages of 18 and 65 years with permanent, mature, single-rooted teeth diagnosed with symptomatic apical periodontitis. The exclusion criteria were multi-rooted teeth, teeth exhibiting internal or external resorption, patients with a known allergy to non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), teeth with severe periodontal disease and teeth with open apices.

Following approval from the College of Physicians & Surgeons Pakistan (CPSP) and the ethical review committee of the institute, a total of 306 patients were planned for recruitment; however only 156 were enrolled due to limited patient availability during the study period. Informed

written consent was obtained from all participants prior to treatment. Preoperative data, including age, sex, tooth number, and pain intensity, were recorded in a pre-designed patient chart. Pain intensity was assessed using the Visual Analog Scale (VAS), with scores ranging from 0 to 10.

Patients were randomly allocated into two groups using the lottery method. Each participant selected one of two sealed envelopes containing group assignments. Group 1 underwent conventional syringe irrigation, while Group 2 received irrigation using the EndoActivator system.

Root canal treatment was carried out in two visits for all patients. During the first visit, all patients received topical anesthesia (Lidocaine 10% Spray Solution, Iran Daru Co., Tehran, Iran) before local anesthesia was administered. A 1.8 mL dose of 2% lidocaine with 1:100,000 epinephrine (Medicine Inj., Huons Co. Ltd, Korea) was injected, and rubber dam isolation was applied. Access cavities were prepared using sterile diamond burs (ISO 016, 25mm, Henry Schein, USA) in a high-speed handpiece. A glide path was established using stainless steel hand instruments. Working length was determined using stainless steel hand K-files size #10 (Mani, Tochigi, Japan) and an apex locator (RootZX II, J. Morita, Tokyo, Japan), with confirmation through periapical radiographs (Digital X-ray, Soredex Digora Optime). All canals were prepared using the step-back technique with conventional stainless steel hand K-files (Mani, Tochigi, Japan) and irrigated with 5.25% sodium hypochlorite. The canals were then dried with sterile paper points, and the tooth was temporized with a sterile cotton pellet and Cavit.

After 48 hours, patients returned for the second visit. Irrigation was repeated as per the group assignment. The canals were dried with sterile paper points and obturated using gutta-percha (Ez Endo, Korea) and sealer (Sealapex, Kerr Endodontics, USA) with the lateral condensation technique. The access cavity was sealed with glass ionomer cement, and the final restoration was completed using composite resin.

Inter-appointment pain for both groups was assessed at 24 and 48 hours via phone calls, using

the VAS. Pain intensity was recorded numerically (0–10), and severity was classified as no pain (0), mild pain (1–3), moderate pain (4–6), or severe pain (7–10). Inter-appointment pain reduction was calculated using the formula:

$$\frac{(\text{Pre-treatment VAS score} - \text{Post-treatment VAS score})}{\text{Pre-treatment VAS score}} \times 100$$
 [9]

No analgesic medications were prescribed immediately after the first visit. Patients were advised to contact the researcher in case of significant discomfort and were strictly instructed not to take any medication without prior consultation. If pain was reported, ibuprofen 200 mg was prescribed as an over-the-counter drug.

Data of the study was entered and analyzed using the SPSS version 22. Mean and standard deviation were calculated for age, pre-operative pain, inter-appointment pain (at 24 hours and 48 hours) and percentage inter-appointment pain reduction (at 24 hours and 48 hours) for each group. Similarly, frequency and percentages were calculated for gender, pain severity, type of tooth, and inter-appointment pain. Both groups were compared using t-test for percentage inter-appointment pain reduction at 24 hours and 48 hours. Effect modifiers/confounders like age, gender and type of tooth were controlled by stratification. Post stratification t-test was applied. P value ≤ 0.05 was considered significant.

RESULTS

A total of 156 patients were included in the study, with equal allocation between the two treatment groups. The demographic and baseline clinical characteristics of the study participants are summarized in **Table 1**. Around half of the participants were aged 35 years or less, premolars constituted the majority of treated teeth, and nearly all participants presented with severe pre-operative pain.

Post-operative pain distribution at 24 and 48 hours is summarized in **Table 2**. The majority of participants reported inter-appointment pain at 24 hours, whereas fewer participants reported pain at 48 hours. Mild pain was the most common pain severity recorded at both follow-up time points.

Comparison of pain scores and percentage pain reduction between the EndoActivator and

conventional irrigation groups is presented in **Table 3**. The EndoActivator irrigation group demonstrated significantly greater percentage pain reduction than the conventional irrigation group at both 24 hours (82.01 ± 14.91 vs. 49.49 ± 12.22 ; $p < 0.001$) and 48 hours (99.17 ± 4.22 vs. 82.64 ± 13.37 ; $p < 0.001$).

Age-stratified analysis is shown in **Table 4**, demonstrating statistically significant differences in percentage pain reduction between the two treatment groups across both age categories at 24 and 48 hours.

Gender-stratified analysis is summarized in **Table 5**, showing statistically significant differences between the two treatment groups among both male and female participants at both follow-up intervals.

Tooth-type stratified analysis is presented in **Table 6**. Statistically significant differences in percentage pain reduction were observed for incisors and premolars at both time points. In canines, a statistically significant difference was observed at 24 hours, whereas no statistically significant difference was found at 48 hours.

Table 1. Demographic and Baseline Clinical Characteristics of Study Participants

Variable	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Total participants	156	100
Age ≤35 years	80	51.3
Age >35 years	76	48.7
Incisors	35	22.4
Canines	16	10.3
Premolars	105	67.3
Moderate pre-operative pain	2	1.3
Severe pre-operative pain	154	98.7

Table 2. Distribution of Inter-Appointment Pain Following Treatment

Variable	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
No pain at 24 hours	29	18.6
Pain present at 24 hours	127	81.4
Mild pain at 24 hours	68	43.6
Moderate pain at 24 hours	58	37.2
Severe pain at 24 hours	1	0.6
No pain at 48 hours	101	64.7
Pain present at 48 hours	55	35.3
Mild pain at 48 hours	55	35.3

Table 3. Comparison of Mean Pain Scores and Percentage Pain Reduction Between Study Groups

Variable	EndoActivator Irrigation Group Mean ± SD	Conventional Irrigation Group Mean ± SD	p-value
Age (years)	32.18 ± 10.03	33.12 ± 10.16	—
Pre-operative pain	8.44 ± 1.08	8.46 ± 1.11	—
Pain at 24 hours	1.53 ± 1.28	4.31 ± 1.20	—
Pain at 48 hours	0.08 ± 0.39	1.51 ± 1.17	—
Percentage pain reduction at 24 hours	82.01 ± 14.91	49.49 ± 12.22	<0.001
Percentage pain reduction at 48 hours	99.17 ± 4.22	82.64 ± 13.37	<0.001

Table 4. Stratified Analysis by Age

Age Group	Inter-appointment Time	EndoActivator Irrigation Group	Conventional Irrigation Group	p-value
≤35 years	24 hours	86.88	49.45	<0.001
≤35 years	48 hours	100.00	82.81	<0.001
>35 years	24 hours	76.62	49.54	<0.001
>35 years	48 hours	98.24	82.46	<0.001

Table 5. Stratified Analysis by Gender

Gender	Inter-appointment Time	EndoActivator Irrigation Group	Conventional Irrigation Group	p-value
Male	24 hours	87.75	50.55	<0.001
Male	48 hours	100.00	87.55	<0.001
Female	24 hours	75.97	48.72	<0.001
Female	48 hours	98.29	79.04	<0.001

Table 6. Stratified Analysis by Tooth Type

Tooth Type	Inter-appointment Time	EndoActivator Irrigation Group	Conventional Irrigation Group	p-value
Incisors	24 hours	83.96	47.90	<0.001
Incisors	48 hours	99.20	77.60	0.001
Canines	24 hours	78.44	57.71	0.045
Canines	48 hours	97.78	89.71	0.176
Premolars	24 hours	81.64	48.81	<0.001
Premolars	48 hours	99.43	82.65	<0.001

DISCUSSION

The present randomized controlled trial demonstrated that the EndoActivator irrigation system produced significantly greater inter-appointment pain reduction than conventional syringe irrigation at both 24 and 48 hours in patients undergoing root canal treatment for symptomatic apical periodontitis. These findings indicate that sonic activation of irrigants may improve short-term postoperative comfort and support the clinical efficacy of adjunctive irrigant activation during endodontic treatment.

Inter-appointment pain following root canal treatment is a well-recognized complication and is generally attributed to acute periapical inflammatory responses initiated by mechanical injury, chemical irritation, microbial persistence,

or apical extrusion of infected debris during instrumentation and irrigation. (10,11) The significantly greater reduction in pain observed in the EndoActivator group in the present study may be explained by the enhanced hydrodynamic agitation and acoustic streaming generated by sonic activation, which improves penetration, circulation, and exchange of irrigants within anatomically complex areas of the root canal system. Such enhanced irrigant dynamics may facilitate superior disruption of microbial biofilm, improved smear layer removal, and more effective elimination of inflammatory substrates that contribute to postoperative pain. (12,13)

The findings of the current study are consistent with those of Ramamoorthi et al., who similarly reported significantly lower postoperative pain

scores in patients treated using EndoActivator-assisted irrigation compared with conventional needle irrigation at both 24 and 48 hours following root canal therapy. (9) Their study concluded that sonic agitation of irrigants improved debridement efficacy and reduced the incidence of postoperative discomfort. Comparable findings have also been reported by Al-Omari et al., who observed that irrigation activation systems were associated with significantly less postoperative pain than conventional irrigation techniques in endodontically treated teeth. (14)

The superior clinical performance of the EndoActivator observed in the present study is biologically plausible and supported by experimental literature. Conventional syringe irrigation, while widely practiced, has recognized limitations including restricted irrigant penetration beyond the needle tip, inability to adequately disrupt vapor lock, and poor debridement of fins, lateral canals, and isthmuses. (15) Gu et al. demonstrated that activated irrigation systems significantly improve irrigant replacement and debris removal compared with syringe irrigation alone. (16) Similarly, van der Sluis et al. reported that sonic and ultrasonic activation techniques improve irrigant penetration into inaccessible root canal irregularities, thereby enhancing canal cleanliness and disinfection. (17) In the present study, stratified analysis demonstrated that the superiority of EndoActivator irrigation remained statistically significant across all age groups and both genders at 24 and 48 hours. This suggests that the beneficial effect of sonic irrigant activation on postoperative pain reduction is likely independent of patient age and gender. Similar observations have been reported in postoperative pain studies where demographic variables were not found to significantly alter the effectiveness of advanced irrigation protocols. (18)

With regard to tooth type, EndoActivator irrigation demonstrated significantly greater pain reduction in incisors and premolars at both time intervals, whereas in canine teeth the difference remained statistically significant only at 24 hours and not at 48 hours. This isolated finding may be

attributable to the relatively small canine subgroup sample size, which may have reduced statistical power and increased the probability of type II statistical error. Alternatively, it may reflect anatomical variation in canine root canal morphology, which can influence irrigant dynamics and debridement efficiency. (19)

The rapid reduction in pain observed in both groups over the 48-hour period is consistent with the established natural course of post-endodontic discomfort, wherein pain intensity typically peaks within the first 24 hours and gradually subsides thereafter. (20) However, the substantially greater magnitude of pain reduction in the EndoActivator group suggests that irrigation technique may play a clinically meaningful role in accelerating symptom resolution beyond the expected natural decline.

Despite the promising findings of this study, certain limitations should be acknowledged. First, although the originally calculated sample size requirement was 306 participants, only 156 patients were recruited due to reduced patient availability during the study period, which may have affected statistical power despite the detection of significant differences. Second, pain assessment was based on patient-reported Visual Analog Scale scores, which, although validated and widely accepted, remain inherently subjective and susceptible to individual variation in pain perception and reporting bias. Third, the study was conducted at a single institution, which may limit the generalizability of findings to broader populations and clinical settings. Finally, operator blinding was not feasible due to the visible differences between irrigation techniques, thereby introducing the possibility of performance bias.

Further multicenter randomized controlled trials with larger sample sizes and extended follow-up durations are recommended to confirm these findings and determine whether the improved short-term pain reduction associated with EndoActivator irrigation also translates into superior long-term endodontic healing outcomes.

CONCLUSION

The present study demonstrated that the EndoActivator irrigation system achieved

significantly greater inter-appointment pain reduction than conventional syringe irrigation at both 24- and 48-hours during root canal treatment in patients with symptomatic apical periodontitis. These findings highlight the potential clinical advantage of sonic irrigant activation in improving short-term postoperative pain outcomes during endodontic treatment

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

Authors declared no conflict of interest.

DISCLOSURE

This manuscript is based on research conducted as part of FCPS-II training requirements in Operative Dentistry and Endodontics.

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PATIENT CONSENT Informed written consent was obtained from all participants prior to enrolment in the study.

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